

MOTIVATION AND BARRIERS TO LEARNING OF STUDENTS: THE CASE OF ONLINE EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study determined the motivation and barriers to learning of the students in the case of online education of Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges Elementary Department, Bogo City, Cebu for the school year 2020-2021. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: What is the level of motivation of the pupils to learn in terms of (a) extrinsic motivation; and (b) intrinsic motivation? What are the levels of barrier to learning as perceived by the respondents in the online distance learning in terms of (a) physical and mental condition; (b) environment; and (c) confidence? The descriptive method was used to identify the motivation and barriers to learning. Their motivation and barriers to online education were tested through an adapted questionnaire. The findings show that there is a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and motivation of learning. The study concluded that the motivation of students in learning online depends upon the external barriers of learning. The participants' perspective shows that the teacher's support and simplified activities and parent's provision of good internet connectivity and the device can make a strong learning motivation. It is recommended that the activities during online class should be very simple because learners have no choice since it is still in a midst of health crisis. Students should be supported in their online classes. Parents, teachers, and other stakeholders shall work together to address the needs of the learners.

Keywords: motivations, barriers to learning, case of online education, support teaching assistance, stakeholders

Introduction

Students were progressively being offered online opportunities for education, whether through modified teaching approaches or increased use of technology even in conventional classrooms. As a result, there is a need to describe the specific challenges that students face while taking online courses, as well as to identify pedagogical methods that can resolve and improve the chances of good online teaching and learning. As provided in the DepEd Order (D.O.) No. 013, s. 2020, the accessibility of learning services, the welfare and well-being of learners and DepEd staff, regional and national directives issued, and the preference of parents and learners are all factors to consider when deciding on particular learning delivery mechanisms to use.

This study identifies and expands on basic aspects of online education that students find to be unclear, posing an obstacle to their learning progress. This study also looked at the disparities in expectations of online classes between students who wanted to take them and those who did not. There had been no research that compared the student approaches of these two groups of students in a single sample. This research aims to find out what differentiates students who want to take online classes from those who don't, as well as to make recommendations for improving the online learning environment. While new technologies have given educators the ability to build several successful learning environments, many young students still prefer traditional academic settings.

Objective of the study

This study aimed to determine the motivation and barriers to learning of the students: The Case of Online Education of Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges Elementary Department, Bogu City Division School Year 2020-2021. Findings served as bases of a proposed action plan.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1. What is the level of motivation of the pupils to learn in terms of: 1.1 extrinsic motivation; and 1.2 intrinsic motivation?

2. What are the levels of barrier to learning as perceived by the respondents in the online distance learning in terms of: 2.1 physical and mental condition; 2.2 environment; and confidence?

Methodology

This study utilized the descriptive – correlational method of research. The study has been conducted at Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges (CRMC) is a private, higher educational institution in Bogu City, Cebu. The 95 students currently enrolled at Cebu Roosevelt Memorial Colleges Elementary Department were the respondents of the study. Out of 123 students, there were only 95 respondents who took the survey questionnaire with the use of convenience sampling. A method of obtaining samples from a site or internet service that is easily accessed. An online survey, adapted by the researcher, was deployed through an online survey tool (i.e., google survey form). The survey items shall be divided into two sections. Items from the first section were designed to collect demographic information including questions about age, gender, status. The purpose of collecting this demographic data was to increase external validity for generalizability applications. The second section of the survey contained items aimed at collecting the information needed to answer the research questions. To gain a better understanding of online course retention rates, participants were asked to respond to an item about their experience with online education. Students responded to items that help the teachers define the important parameters for creating an effective learning environment. Students were asked to rate various scenarios assisted by the teacher and/or parents from strongly disagree to strongly agree on a 6-point Likert-type scale (Likert, 1932).

A few examples include: whether students feel isolated in an online class, whether students get confused in an online class, and whether students enjoy participating in online discussions. Data collected from the Likert-type scale items help the researcher discover the student learner attitudes

related to challenges, and therefore best or worst approaches, to delivering content and communicating in online classes. There was a pilot test done in Medellin Central School before this study was conducted in the CRMC Elementary department. Cronbach alpha result of this study is found in the appendix. The data for this thesis was taken from the elementary department of CRMC. The link form from the Google survey sent through messenger to the student recipients helped provide familiarization with the goal of the study, which contained an informed consent statement. The consent statement also informed the recipients about the researcher's name as well as the name of the researcher's advisor and contact details.

This information allowed students the opportunity to contact either the researcher or the researcher's academic advisor if they have any questions or concerns regarding the survey. The statement also made clear that participation in the study is optional. Recipients began the survey and were informed that they could quit participating at any time with no consequences. The link message also noted that the researcher would not be collecting or obtaining identifying data. This information was made available to survey recipients before they could decide to follow the survey link to participate in the study. The first research question aimed at determining student barriers to online education, regardless of a desire or intention to take an online course in the future, did not require a comparison between the four groups. The purpose of this question was to explore any barriers all students can have, regardless of their desire to take an online course or not. The first research question was accounted for all of the respondents who may not have a choice of taking or not taking an online course. To increase the validity of the data for the first research question, frequencies for answers were calculated and analyzed. The second research question aimed at answering whether a significant difference exists between variables.

Results and Discussion

This study revealed that most of the respondents are aged 11, 12, and 9. There were more female respondents than males. The family income reflected in this study implied that most respondents belong to middle-class level family. This study revealed that the majority of the students like to see a complete online course in the first week they can work at their own pace. They also prefer to get just one week of the course material at a time and get ample opportunity to demonstrate their learning in online sessions. Moreover, most students prefer face-to-face to online classes because they lose control when the internet is lousy and get frustrated when they cannot do their task online. This study also revealed that students want online classes to have a sense of community among students and instructors. Most of the respondents' value participating in online class discussions and like to have a class portfolio to complete. However, most of them easily get confused during online class sessions and felt aloft and isolated while having their online classes. This study further revealed that most students love to know the feedback of their instructors; they also felt comfortable using new technologies and considered themselves to be good with Internet-related technologies. This study showed that the majority of the respondents does not have enough time to study due to busy work. It also revealed that they felt the tuition fees are too high and they have become a serious financial burden to them. Furthermore, the majority of them believes that their family and friends do not support their studies. This study also reflected that students easily get distracted by the background noise during online class sessions but on the other hand they believe that they can finish this school year easily and they love to answer questions presented by their teachers online. This study also revealed the relationship between respondents' profile and their learning motivation. It was found out that there was no significant relationship between the variables in terms of age, gender, and family income to extrinsic reward and extrinsic punishment as well as the intrinsic reward and intrinsic punishment. This means that the respondents' profile does not matter in terms of learning motivation. Learners

who focus on learning rather than performance or who have intrinsic motivation to learn to tend to set goals for themselves and regard increasing their competence to be a goal. Nonetheless, the results revealed that they do not correlate with each other as presented above.

This also revealed the relationship between respondents' profile and the barriers to learning. The results showed that there was no significant relationship in terms of age, and family income with physical, environmental, and confidence. However, only the environment has a significant relationship to gender negligibly which failed to reject H_0 with physical and confidence.

Finally, this study revealed the relationship between motivation to learning and barriers to learning. It was reflected that there was a significant relationship between extrinsic reward and extrinsic punishment with physical, environmental, and confidence. Moreover, there was also a significant correlation between intrinsic reward with physical, environmental, and confidence. However, intrinsic punishment was only significantly correlated in the physical and environmental aspects but not in confidence.

Conclusion

The external barriers of learning depend mostly upon the motivation of students in learning. Motivation is a fundamental springboard toward a better teaching-learning process and can make learning more meaningful even with online classes. Furthermore, in the field of research, motivation is henceforth a factor to consider in breaking barriers to learning. To identify differences between and within gender classes, schools must collect and monitor academic achievement and course enrollment by gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. Teachers should have student profile upon enrollment and conduct interviews among students and parents. School heads should ensure that this is followed and disseminated before the opening of classes. Teachers are also encouraged to provide clearer directions to students so that they would not get confused during online class sessions. Parents are encouraged to support their children's online education and unload their burden at homework. They should help their students focus on school activities. School administrators are recommended not to increase tuition fees and miscellaneous fees in times of pandemic. Family and friends of the students should show support and encourage the students to learn despite the online class modality. Teachers are encouraged to ensure quality online class by removing or clearing background noise during online class sessions. Parents are recommended to buy noise cancelling device for their students not to get distracted. Local Government Officials are encouraged to pass an ordinance to prohibit videoke sessions and other unnecessary things that cause noises and affect the neighborhood. Teachers should provide enrichment activities for students since the students love the activities provided by the teachers. Administrators should help their teachers ensure quality online classes by providing them with good internet and fast processor devices.

Recommendations

It is recommended that teachers provide intrinsic motivational activities for students and involve parents in doing such. It is also recommended that administrators should make programs that would motivate learners intrinsically and shall be funded by the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses(MOOE) of the school. It is recommended to teachers to create a supportive learning environment for the students. The school heads are encouraged to tap private entities and other benevolent sponsors to make this possible. Curriculum makers should create a curriculum that is aligned with the needs of the learners and supports an ideal learning environment. This does not only mean a clean, well-decorated classroom but it also means a harmonious relationship among students and teachers and a school that is a zone of peace. It is therefore recommended to teachers to create and ensure the physical, environmental, and confidence aspect learning experience of the students so that they could not be affected by some barriers of learning. It is further recommended to adapt the proposed

action plan of this study because parents can make or unmake the future of their students and parental involvement is very important in designing simplified activities for the students in online class modality. The teacher can tailor tools to a specific group of pupils' needs. This method is also consistent with the instructor's job in an online course, which is to facilitate productive collaboration and interaction. Future study could focus on tools that assist first-time students in online learning environments. Additionally, holding a focus group with a chosen group of students could provide more help to the researcher to go deeper into subtler inquiries about different technologies and online learning experiences. Online courses are fast expanding, and research into collaborative technologies, should be undertaken on a regular basis to ensure that a course is aligned with evidence-based practices

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